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Vocational Education and Training offered in Second Chance Schools in Spain: Possibilities and Limits from an Organizational Analysis

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Abstract

The paper provides theoretical and empirical analysis of how second chance schools are addressing the challenge of early school leaving through provision of vocational training and vocational and personal guidance.

Our research context is provided by accredited second chance schools in Spain, which are undergoing an external evaluation process since 2017 which is also part of the strategy that these schools have to gain visibility, respect, legitimation and funding as well by education and employment administrations.

Our theoretical approach builds upon South American literature on the weight of the institutional dimension in providing formal and non-formal vocational training, in an attempt to differentiate what are the crucial elements of the curriculum and the organization of training that introduce differences in what seems to be otherwise a similar vocational offer. We focus upon five different aspects, one of them clearly curricular (training itself) while the other four are more likely organizational: selection and admission processes; intermediation processes as training comes to an end; networking with other organizations that receive or submit young students to second chance schools; and the organizational culture, values and identity that help stressing differences among institutions. We also rely upon five quality criteria: pertinence, relevance, integrality, efficacy and efficiency, that are explained in relation to the appropriateness of training for the needs of the labor market, the students, and the means available to organizations.

We apply that framework to analyze 18 second chance schools in several Spanish regions, in order to assess how different they are and how relevant the organizational culture is.

Keywords

second chance schools, quality, fight against early school leaving, organization

1 Introduction

Early school leaving is a relevant problem of European educational policy, and it has been a major problem in Spain since the shift of the century, though the crisis in the past decade have contributed to solve it as returning to education was perceived as an acceptable option for many. The problem does not only lie upon individuals, but also on the features of education systems and the loss of legitimacy in present times (Alexander, Loewenthal and Butt, 2020).

In 2016, the Spanish Association of Second Chance Schools was founded to tackle this problem, according to similar experiences developed in France and in parallel to similar developments taking place in Portugal. The notion of second chance schools, coined by the European Union in the mid 1990s, has been researched by Kiprianos & Mpourgos (2020), and Paniagua (2022), and it has been one of the several measures adopted to retain or re-enrol students in the system, particularly through vocational training and practice-based programs (Williamson, 2014).

2 Theoretical framework

Jacinto and Milenaar (2009) have shown the relevance of institutional factors affecting the pedagogical quality of vocational training programs that reengage students in education. Based upon their work and that of González (2003), who addresses the organizational dimensions of schools as relevant facilitators of pedagogical interventions, we have devised a framework to analyse the quality of the provision of vocational programs in their relation to the demands of students with specific needs.

This framework embeds the five quality criteria suggested by Jacinto (1998): Pertinence (adequacy to the qualification demands of the labour market); relevance (adequacy to the expectations and needs of the youth); integral offer (both in terms of valid and wide qualifications that comprise technical and social skills as well as in terms of social and support actions that provide the conditions for learning processes to happen); efficacy; and efficiency. These criteria will allow us to identify different kinds of second chance provision, under the assumption that there is no one best second chance school, but that their success depends upon selection and matching criteria where the offer of the school is appropriate to respond to the demands of young people and to foster them to increase their personal and social development and their own employability.

By doing so, we take forward upon the studies of Martínez-Morales (2021) and consider other experiences where the institutional is relevant such as Calvo, Gutiérrez and Bayarri (2020) and Martins et al. (2020) have done too. We opt for an organizational perspective rather than a didactical or methodological one. We do not want to focus on curriculum design and development, neither on the way that vocational training is delivered. Rather, we want to look at the way in which the institutions are constituted and what is the rationale guiding the decisions they take in the mid and long-term.

Given that we have conducted research with second chance schools in Spain since 2019, this has helped us develop several hypotheses that we are currently studying with these institutions:

1. We expect that Covid-19 has affected the vocational offer, considering that certain occupations are no longer as attractive as before and that some were considered as essential services during lockdown. Perhaps, second chance schools have attempted to diversify their offer to address more seriously both telework as digitalisation. Perhaps the gender division of work has been further affected by this. Furthermore, digitalisation might have an impact upon their methodologies, not just content.
2. Second chance schools offer of vocational qualifications tend to retain students until they achieve these qualifications, while those which are not accredited to provide a formal VET qualification tend to accelerate access into the labour market of their students or to make them return to the education system. We expect also to find second chance schools whose main priority is not access into the labour market nor return into the education system, but rather personal reconstruction and development of the adolescent.
3. We expect to find differences between second chance schools who are part of a larger organization that offer other educational and social support and those where the whole

organization is a second chance school, the former being able to adapt their vocational offer to a larger extent than the latter, which are subject to the staff that is member of the organization.

4. We expect differences in the awareness and update of labour market needs among second chance schools. According to this and their own vocational offer, we expect second chance schools to avoid access of those youth whose interest are not covered by their qualifications. Furthermore, schools that have programs to allow students explore their vocational interest and follow their own pathway accordingly, even if this means leaving the second chance school.

5. All second chance schools gather at least two of the three first quality criteria suggested by Jacinto (1999), that is, pertinence, relevance, and integral offer; and at least one of the two latter criteria (either efficacy or efficiency). These are the foundations for their success.

6. Accordingly, attraction and selection processes of second chance schools are conducted intentionally to make the best out of their limited chances. Second chance schools keep registration open all year through, to serve the needs of young people who have dropped the formal education system or newcomers, given the amount of migrant population that they enrol (up to a third of their whole registration). This is possible given the variety of their offer, consisting often of non-formal vocational training as well as other complementary support such as housing, leisure, and others.

7. Second chance schools take part of networks with other organizations that are active in the beginning, whenever there is selection and access into the second chance school, but also in their final stages, when it comes to look for work placements for students and for facilitating access into the labour market or return to the education system.

8. The institutional identity and prestige of the second chance school is well-known in its environment, it remains stable, and it makes of them a resource to which social and educational organizations address whenever they have youth that might benefit from attendance to second chance schools.

9. We expect to find, whatever the differences, certain features in all second chance schools that facilitate innovation processes within them.

To analyse our hypothesis, we have developed an overarching framework to analyse the study of these educational organizations, which comprises the following dimensions:

- Context in which the school is located. Although most accredited second chance schools are located in urban areas, we search for differences among large and small cities, where the role of industrial, agriculture and service economies is different.

- Intervention strategies. We embed training provision as one more process within a wider intervention rationale, that we divide in three steps.

- o First, the actions taken by the organization to approach, select and welcome new students that they want to enrol.

- o Second, the training provision itself, how it evolves and what are the dimensions it covers. We do not just focus upon training, but also take into consideration what makes training possible. Therefore, by training provision we understand the following:

- Vocational training that is conducive to accredited qualifications

- Vocational training that is merely non-formal training and that achieves no official recognition even if it qualifies the young person

- Academic education such as instrumental skills in languages, maths, and another basic cultural knowledge

- Personal development assistance such as emotional intelligence, social skills, affective or sexual education, education in leisure activities

- Non-curricular support provided to youth, be it housing, legal assistance, financial aid, health support or others. Adaptative measures to Covid-19 are also considered here

○ Third, all the preparation addressed to facilitate the young person leaving the organization with chances to succeed in adult and working life. This includes several actions such as guidance, intermediation, and follow-up of the young person's trajectory:

- Work placement and access into the labour market
- Return to formal vocational education
- Network with other institutions where the young person can proceed with

other forms of specialized support that may be needed and that cannot be provided by the second chance school

- Teaching-learning processes, where we look to how the curriculum is designed and developed, which are the methods employed by the staff and what is the role of technology in the educational process¹

- Relations with other education, social and work institutions in the area, where we look at networks among organizations, and also how they handle the balance between cooperation and competition with those that are similar to them

- Institutional identity of the second chance school, where we consider the main features of their organizational culture, what are their values and mission and how do these relate to their original constituency, be it an association, foundation or cooperative (as a legal form) and be it promoted by a religious institution or a civil one.

Those are therefore the issues we have been looking at when approaching second chance schools and the variables that have guided our data-gathering process so that we could end up with a proper interpretation of the keys behind the success of each of the schools as well as with the basis to compare different schools among them.

3 Methodology

The research we report in this paper is part of a larger study that attempts to cover the relation between offer and demand in second chance schools in Spain. There are currently 45 accredited second chance schools, they are present in 10 Spanish regions: Andalucía, Aragón, Basque country, Canary Islands, Castilla – La Mancha, Castilla – León, Catalonia, Madrid, Navarra and the Valencian Community. To conduct our study of the organizations, we have got permission from 18 schools located in seven different regions. We have also involved 29 of them in our quantitative study, where we are conducting a longitudinal study consisting of the application of questionnaires among students enrolled in these schools in three different moments in school years 2021/2022 and 2022/2023.

However, this paper focuses on the side of the offerings. We have gathered documentation of the 18 schools willing to participate in our study, from different sources:

- The accreditation reports produced by the accreditation committee of the Spanish Association of Second Chance Schools, as well as the self-evaluation reports produced by the schools in that process.
- Data with all the offerings of the schools since they were accredited (starting 2017) until schoolyear 2020-2021.
- Relevant internal documents produced by the school dealing with their educational proposal, internal rules, internal handbooks or teachers, selection criteria of students and teachers, assessment criteria of students learning, as well as others.
- Documentation available in the websites of the non-for-profit organizations that back second chance schools, including how they marketize themselves, the year reports of what they have done, their networks, their different policies (on gender, bullying, etc.) as well as position documents of the organizations.

¹ These results will be not addressed in this paper

We analysed all the documents and have produced individual reports of each schools that have been validated by staff in the schools, in order to make sure that our interpretation is not mistaken due to missing information and/or misunderstandings. Our reports are shaped with the framework we have devised and presented above.

4 Findings

Our findings are being subject of discussion within the research group at the time of writing this paper, and they will be shared with the schools in the national gathering they have in late April 2023.

So far, we have been able to apply our analytical framework and apply it to compare the different organizational features of the schools; then deciding on how the five quality criteria result in each of them and third; daring to state whether our assumptions were right or wrong.

Let us present first some basic features of the 18 schools analysed in our sample:

School 1, West Spain. It is school promoted by a Foundation, inspired by the Salesian Christian religious order, serving the needs of young people coming from all over the region, as it is equipped with a residence.

School 2, North Spain. It is a school promoted by a Foundation, inspired by a movement of Catholic lays but registered as a civil organization. This Foundation has several second chance schools in different regions, and vocational education and training is at the core of their action.

School 3, North Spain. It is a school promoted by the local authorities in a rural area, with the aim to contribute to its local development in both social and economic terms, employing non-formal vocational training for this purpose.

Schools 4 and 5, North Spain. These are schools promoted by a cooperative of workers, most of them teachers, who have several locations within the region, often located in industrial parks, where they offer both formal and non-formal vocational education.

School 6, North Spain. It is an association with two vocational training sites in a large city.

School 7, East Spain. It is a school promoted by a Foundation, located in a large city and its main provision is vocational training, formal and non-formal.

School 8, 9 and 10, East Spain. These are promoted by three different Foundations, one of which (school 8) is a major player in the vocational training market, while the Foundations behind schools 9 and 10 are recognized for the social services they provide in different domains and different age populations. They all offer formal and non-formal vocational training, and they are all located in the same city as school 7.

Schools 11 and 12, Nort-East Spain. School 11 is promoted by a young civil Foundation, and it is one of the few among our sample where the second chance school and the organization itself are the same and undifferentiated. School 12 is promoted by a Catholic religious order and intends to serve the needs of vulnerable young people and their families. Both are active in a large metropolitan area.

School 13 is promoted by a civil association, it a large city in central Spain, and it has several locations serving the needs of different kinds of people in vulnerable situations. The school offers non-formal vocational training.

School 14 is promoted by the same Foundation as school 2, but located in a Eastern city in the country. It offers formal and non-formal vocational training.

School 15 is an association and, the same as school 11, one of the few where the second chance school and the organization are one and the same. It has several locations where it offers social support, basic education, and formal and non-formal vocational training.

School 16 is promoted by an association in a Southern touristic town, but the main location of this association is in a different city in the Southern coast. It offers mainly careers guidance and facilitates work placements.

Schools 17 and 18 are promoted by a Foundation set by a Catholic religious order and they are in two different southern cities, with different social and industrial fabric, so that they appear to be rather different organizations even if they both offer non-formal vocational training and basic education.

In table 1, we summarize the main findings according to the organizational dimensions of our framework; while in table 2 we synthetize the quality criteria as identified in the schools. In some cases, we could not gather appropriate information and therefore we have indicated so with the sign – in the table.

Table 1

Organizational dimensions of second chance schools

	Selection	Training	Intermediation	Networks	Organizational culture
1	Admin.	Several VET qualifications	Placements	Social and employment	Working culture
2	Intentional recruitment	Diversified VET qualifications	Companies hiring	Social and educational	Local neighbourhood
3	Migrant youth	Traditional VET qualifications	-	Local reach	Public resource
4	Intentional recruitment	VET & basic education	Limited	Limited	Dependent
5	Intentional recruitment	Limited VET qualifications	Limited	Social services	Local resource
6	Intentional and limited	Diversified VET qualifications	Vocational exploration	Companies and public administration	Special education needs
7	Administration & intentional	Limited VET qualifications	Individualized	Coordination	Social and work recognition
8	Administration	Limited VET qualifications	Guidance as the key	Cooperation	Political foundation
9	Intentional	Diversified VET qualifications	Personal, labour, and academic guidance	Strong relation to companies	Strong cohesion and professionalism
10	Intentional	Wide and diversified VET qualifications	Expert vocational guidance	Strong relation to companies	Social and work recognition, professionalism
11	Intentional	Diversified VET qualifications	Focused upon work placements	Strong administrative support	High presence in social media, digitalisation, positive view
12	Those with no other chances	Limited VET qualification	Personal, labour, and academic guidance	Sufficient cooperation	Relevant social and local recognition
13	Open system	Limited VET qualification Digitalization	Labour orientation	Cooperation with companies	Changing identity
14	Intentional	Limited VET qualification Basic education	Personal, labour, and academic guidance	Social and public networks	Social recognition Individual support
15	Intentional	VET qualification Basic education	Personal, labour, and academic guidance	Strong cooperation with companies	Relevant social and local recognition

16	Open system	Basic education	Vocational guidance	Work placements	Employment agency
17	Intentional	Basic education	Support in different life domains	Dependent upon Foundation	Employment agency
18	Intentional	Vocational training	Support in different life domains	Internal to foundation	Internal to foundation Employment agency

Table 2
Quality criteria

	Pertinence	Relevance	Integral	Efficacy	Efficiency
1	-	Short training Placement	Training Employment Psychosocial	X	Networking
2	Local cluster	VET not demanded	Skills of all kinds	Limited	Optimal
3	Local needs	Accredited qualification	Legal support	Successful	Optimal
4	Local cluster	Limited given access criteria	Skills of all kinds	Successful	Optimal
5	Local cluster	Relevant	Skills of all kinds	Successful	Optimal
6	Local cluster	Highly relevant, adapted	Overall personal and social emancipation	Successful	Optimal
7	Reengagement in education	Choice of VET qualification	Family financial support	Successful	Optimal
8	Uneven according to qualification	Sufficient	Basic support	Relative success	Optimal, very well resourced
9	-	-	-	Successful	-
10	Labour market needs	-	-	-	Optimal
11	Local needs	Vocational accreditation of migrants	Social and personal support	-	Optimal
12	Locally rooted	Focused upon language competence	Strong support in different life domains	Successful	Optimal
13	Digital competencies	Short-term training	Loose support	Successful	Networking
14	Uneven vocational qualification Basic education	Focused upon personal accompaniment	Strong support in different life domains	Successful	Optimal and stressed
15	Vocational qualification Basic education	Focused upon personal accompaniment	Strong support in different life domains	Successful	Optimal and stressed
16	Local needs	Basic education Qualification	Vocational guidance	Relatively successful	Optimal
17	Uneven	Personal development	Strong support in different life domains	Successful	Optimal
18	Uneven	Emancipation	Strong support in different life domains	Relatively successful	Optimal

We finalize our presentation of findings by referring to the assumptions upon which our research is being carried out:

Schools' offerings are more tied to the equipment and staff available in the school than to the interest of the students that register in the school.

Institutions have a weight upon the organizational identity of the schools, but most schools have been able to develop its own organizational culture that makes them different from other schools promoted by the same institution. This happens due to staff hiring policies, to the facilities of the organization, its location within the cities they are and the kind of youth they enrol.

There are no differences in the VET provision according to the religious/lay background of the institutions promoting second chance schools. There are no differences either in relation to the other VET providers in the same geographical area.

Schools manage to select their students so as to maximize the opportunities they have to be attracted to the vocational field in which they are qualifying. Therefore, they can all be considered as successful in terms of efficacy.

5 Discussion

The initial analysis of the 18 second chance schools points in the direction of finding different organizational arrangements that reflect both the adaptation to the circumstances of the context in which the schools are located (both labour market as competitor schools) as well as it is the result of the institutional identity of the school, which plays a major role because in most cases the institution offers other services than those of the second chance schools

We end our contribution with an attempt to present the basis of a possible typology of second chance schools, able to show differences worth considering in their ability to serve the needs to a diverse population in different regional and local contexts.

1. Schools addressing particularly youth of migrant origin and unaccompanied minors. Here we find schools with number 1, 5, 11, 17 and 18. Given the legal situation of these youth, these schools work in close relation to residential services, and they emphasize not just the language preparation of the youth and their professional qualification, but also the need to cover for other ordinary areas of everyday life that those youth living with their families usually do not need.
2. Schools with a strong orientation towards facilitating access into the labour market.
3. Here we identify schools with number 2, 4, 8, 13, 15 and 16. These are schools that might well act as employment agencies, and they tend to establish relations to company either for placements or for hiring after the training. Furthermore, we can differentiate those who work upon vocational exploration and guidance from those who offer a wide variety of qualifications, even non-formal and non-accredited, but that increase the employability of their youth.
4. Schools with a strong focus upon the personal and social needs of the youth they serve.
5. Schools with numbers 4, 6, 9, 10, 12 and 14 tend to have intentional selection processes that they use to provide youth with a relevant and integral provision, that ranks higher than pertinence of the offer.
6. Schools with a strong link to the area in which they work.
7. These are schools which have been in the same neighbourhood for many years and whose work is focused upon youth from the area, that are well recognised among employers and schools in it and that play a key role using their networks to facilitate becoming adults. Schools number 2, 3, 6, 12, 14 fall under this category.
8. Schools with a strong dependency of the institution promoting them.
9. There is a final group of schools that are either depending on the institutions behind them, as the case of 4, 5, 16 and 17. Even if it is not the same, we can also state that schools with

numbers 7, 9 and 10 share a similar pattern given the work they do in the city in which they are located.

A final word to mention that we are currently discussing our reports with the schools and we attempt to present first results that might lead to reconsidering some of our interpretations exposed in this paper.

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Biographical note

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